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“MEMORIES OF YESTERDAY”

Yesterday, I woke up at 7:00 AM as my phone alarm rang. I pressed to stop button and sat on the edge of the bed. My feet touched the floor, and it felt cool against my skin.

I walk to the kitchen and flipped on the light switch. A soft yellow glow filled the room. Opening the refrigerator, I felt a rush of cold water. I took a glass from the shelf and poured myself some water.

The water was refreshingly cold. I set the glass on the sink, leaving tiny droplets clinging to its surface. Glancing at the wall clock, I saw it was 7:15 AM.

Back on my room, I opened the closet and chose a blue shirt and black pants. I dressed myself carefully, buttoning the shirt neatly.

I sat down at the table, where an open notebook lay waiting, with a pen resting beside it. I pick up the pen, its ink was deep black, and wrote the date at the top of the page.

I jotted down three short lines, nothing the things I had done that morning. When I finished, I closed the notebook and placed the pen gently on its cover.

Standing up, I walk to the window and drew back the curtain. Bright daylight streamed through the glass. Outside stood a tree, its leaves rich and green.

A moment later, I hear a knock at the door. I walked over, turned the knob, and opened it. Someone stood there and greeted me; I said hello in return.

We chatted briefly for about five minutes before they said goodbye and left. I closed the door and turned the lock, then returned to my seat.

I look once more at the notebook and pen resting on the table. The light was still on. As I reached to switch it off, yesterday came to a quiet, gentle end.

